

Temperature variation and its influence on pH, dissolved oxygen (DO) and free carbondioxide (CO₂) of Nissan pond at Vengurla, Sindhudurg District, (MS).

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ABSTRACT

Temperature is an important factor that affects the chemical and biological reactions in water. Temperature regulates self-purification capacity of water (Shaikh and Yeragi, 2003). A rise in water temperature accelerates chemical reactions which in turn reduces solubility of gases and also elevates metabolism of aquatic organisms, leading to decrease in dissolved oxygen and increase in free carbon dioxide. The present study was carried out on Nissan Pond in Vengurla taluka of Sindhudurg district in Maharashtra. In this study effect of varying temperature on parameters like pH, dissolved oxygen, free carbon dioxide, was observed for the period of two years from January 2012 to December 2013.

Keywords: Temperature influence, Nissan Pond, Vengurla.

INTRODUCTION

Study of physical, chemical and biological aspects of freshwater ecology is called limnology. Water is the survival medium of all living organisms and hence required for the existence of all living organisms. Water as a powerful solvent, most of the substances get readily soluble in it and hence water composition is very much prone to changes due to the unwanted substances. Every living organisms demands for clean, unpolluted water for its survival. Change in water composition influences the abundance and diversity of biota of that aquatic ecosystem. Anthropogenic activities of man deteriorates the water quality of water resources in close vicinity of the human civilization and hence these freshwater resources are always prone to pollution, putting forth a question of water quality and safety concerned with public health.

Interaction between some important parameters like temperature, pH, dissolved oxygen and free carbon dioxide were studied at Nissan Pond in Vengurla taluka of Sindhudurg district. Vengurla (15.85°00'52.2"N, 73.63°22'81.2"E) is a taluka place in Sindhudurg district of Maharashtra state, India. It is surrounded by a semicircular range of hills with lush green foliage mainly of cashew, mango, coconut and different kinds of berry trees. The taluka has a rich cultural heritage. It is famous for its beaches and beautiful temples. Vengurla, being a safe and natural port, commercial center was initially established during 1665 by Dutch traders and subsequently by British rulers. Planned city having roads and drainage system, market commercial and office buildings, Municipal Council, Hospitals, Parks, etc. was developed by British rulers. Vengurla Municipal Council is one of the Oldest Municipal Council in Maharashtra state. It has an average elevation of 11m. The climate here is tropical monsoon climate. The highest temperature in summer

reaches 42°C while in winter temperature drops to 15°C. The population during 2001 census was recorded as 12,471.

Nissan pond is located 10km at outskirts of Vengurla. It rains heavily during monsoon from June to September and water gets collected in the pond. The pond remains full throughout the year fulfilling the water requirements of the Vengurla. The pond is surrounded by a dense vegetation (Figure 1) of mango, cashew. Coconut, jackfruit and other trees thus making a good nesting place for different birds. Also migratory birds are reported during the November to February. Water of the pond is supplied to Vengurla from the huge tank built at opposite side of the pond (Figure 2).

Figure 1: Nissan Pond, Vengurla

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Water samples for the estimation were collected in first week of every month from January 2012 to December 2013. The samples were collected in clean one liter can in morning hours between 7.00 am to 10.00 am. The parameters temperature and pH was measured on the spot. The water sample for dissolved oxygen estimation was separately collected in 300ml BOD bottles and DO was fixed on the spot. All the samples were carefully transported to laboratory and the further analysis was carried out immediately employing methods described by Trivedy and Goel (1986), APHA (1992) and Kodarkaret al (1998).

Figure 2: Water tank, Vengurla

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The physico-chemical parameters like temperature, pH, dissolved oxygen, free carbon dioxide are considered to be important as far as the quality of the waterbody is concerned. Hence the variations in following parameters were studied during the period of two years January 2012 to December 2013. The data recorded during the study is presented in table 1.

Temperature:

Temperature is considered to be one of the important abiotic factor of any waterbody. According to Sirsathet *al* (2011) temperature studies not only give idea of self –purification of rivers, reservoirs and control of treatment plant but also play an important role in influencing the periodicity, occurrence and abundance of phytoplankton. The water temperature recorded during January 2012 to December 2013 ranged in between 21°C to 34°C. Minimum temperature was recorded during the winter season ranging I between 21°C to 28°C. This may be to low absorbance of solar radiation because of cool atmosphere during winter. Maximum temperature (29°C to 34°C) was recorded from March to June. Vengurla taluka experience hot summers from March to May. This leads to vaporization of pond water in summer and water level also decreases causing rise in surface water temperature. Jakher and Rawat (2003) recorded temperature 15°C to 38°C at a Tropical Lake, Jodhpur. Similar results were also recorded by some other workers like Mishra *et al* (2007) at

Table 1: Monthly variations recorded in parameters like temperature, pH, dissolved oxygen, free carbondioxide during January 2012 to December 2013 at Nissan Pond, Vengurla.

Sr. No.	Parameters	Temperature °C		pH		Dissolved oxygen mg/L		Free Carbondioxide mg/L	
		2012	2013	2012	2013	2012	2013	2012	2013
1.	January	24	27	8.1	8.1	6.00	6.09	0.25	0.24
2.	February	21	26	8.8	8.7	5.62	5.86	0.30	0.35
3.	March	29	29	8.1	8.3	6.01	5.01	0.29	0.33
4.	April	30	30	7.8	7.9	5.06	4.93	0.62	0.61
5.	May	33	34	7.9	7.9	4.85	4.52	0.60	0.58
6.	June	30	32	7.5	7.5	4.67	4.64	0.64	0.65
7.	July	31	31	7.4	7.3	4.91	4.91	0.51	0.56
8.	August	29	30	7.3	7.4	5.20	5.20	0.37	0.42
9.	September	30	31	7.4	7.4	6.09	5.96	0.22	0.22
10.	October	29	28	7.2	7.2	8.49	8.05	0.21	0.21
11.	November	28	25	7.4	7.5	8.83	8.83	0.22	0.20
12.	December	26	24	7.8	7.9	9.40	9.42	0.20	0.21

Ulhas River; Gonjari and Patil (2008) at Triputi Reservoir, Satara; Das and Shrivastava (1956) at lucknow; Prakash (1994) at Mehta Pond, Jhabua; Dave *et al* (1999) at Kalika pond, Dhar.

pH:

In present study the pH ranged in between 7.2 to 8.8 indicating alkaline nature of the Nissan pond. WHO (1984) has recommended desirable pH values of drinking water as 7.0 to 8.5. The maximum pH values were recorded in summer season while minimum in rainy and winter season. Khaireet *al* (2011) recorded pH between 8.1 to 8.7 at Mehakari reservoir, and also stated that temperature brings out changes in pH. Most of the workers Shaikh and Yeragi (2003) recorded pH value ranging from 7.04 to 8.43 in Tansa river, Thane; Kedar and Patil (2002) in Rishi Lake at Karanja; Khedkar and Dixit (2003) observed pH ranged in between 6.5 to 8.4 at Amravati. Anderson (1961) reported important role of pH in formation of algal bloom at trophic lake, Washington have recorded higher pH during summer season and lower pH at winters showing direct relation between pH and temperature. Higher pH during summer season may be due to decrease in water level which elevates the water temperature, but higher pH values during winter season may be due to increase in number of phytoplankton due to high values of dissolved oxygen in winter. Lower pH values were observed in monsoon season may be

due to high turbidity caused by flooding of waterbody which elevates water temperature and decreases the photosynthetic activity resulting in accumulation of free carbondioxide (Adebisi, 1980).

Dissolved oxygen:

Life, whether aquatic or terrestrial requires oxygen to breathe. Aquatic organisms utilize oxygen which is dissolved in water in their vicinity. Oxygen gets into the water from air by the process of diffusion and as result of photosynthesis carried out by aquatic plants.

Mishra and Yadav (1978) referred dissolved oxygen as pulse of an aquatic ecosystem which influences biochemical changes and effects metabolic activities of organisms. In present study higher dissolved oxygen values were recorded in winter season and comparatively lower values in rainy and summer season. Higher values of dissolved oxygen during winter season may be due to lower temperature which elevates the photosynthetic activity of chlorophyll containing life. During summer and rainy season increase in temperature was reported which resulted lower oxygen holding capacity of waterbody. Many workers Bharti and Kori (1975) at Dharwad; Dutta *et al* (2001) in Basantar river at Jammu Kashmir; Chavanet *al* (2005) at Manjra reservoir, Beed; Bahura (1998) at Temple tank, Bikaner; Kamble and Muley

Figure 3: Monthly variation in temperature during Jan 2012 - Dec, 2013.

Figure 4: Monthly variation in pH during Jan 2012 - Dec, 2013.

Figure 5: Monthly variation in dissolved oxygen during Jan 2012 – Dec, 2013.

(2008) at Kalbadevi estuary, Ratnagiri; Sakhare and Joshi (2003) at Papnas, Tuljapur reported inverse relation between temperature and dissolved oxygen supporting the present findings. Wetzel (1975) stated that dissolved oxygen affects solubility and availability of the nutrients which greatly influences the productivity of the ecosystem.

Free Carbondioxide:

Welch (1952) has stated free carbondioxide as an extremely necessary constituent in an aquatic ecosystem. Considerable amount of carbondioxide is produced due to the respiratory activity of aquatic organisms which is dissolved in the water while some of it is let into the atmosphere. In present study free carbondioxide ranged in between 0.2 mg/L to 0.65mg/L. higher values of free carbondioxide were recorded in rainy and summer season while lower values

Figure 6: Monthly variation in free carbon dioxide during Jan 2012 – Dec, 2013.

were obtained during winter season. Todda (1970) and Cole (1979) explained lower values of carbondioxide in winter are due to decrease in temperature which elevates the oxygen holding capacity of the waterbody due to increased photosynthetic activity by phytoplanktons but higher carbondioxide values during summer season are due to decomposition of organic matter. Vyas and Kumar (1968); Bahura (1998) at Temple tank, Bikaner; Telkhadeet *al* (2011) reported direct relationship of free carbondioxide with temperature and pH but an inverse relationship with dissolved oxygen supporting the present findings.

CONCLUSION

The study at Nissan Pond in Vengurla Taluka showed that temperature being important physical parameter greatly influences the chemical parameters like pH, dissolved oxygen and free carbon dioxide. The study is also supported by many researchers. Temperature is directly proportional with the parameters like pH and free carbon dioxide while inversely proportional with the values of dissolved oxygen.

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